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Legal Relations in Healthcare Services in Indonesia; Perspective from Law No.17 of 2023 Concerning Health

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Abstract: This article explains the legal relationship in the provision of health services. The juridical-normative research method is used. The data used in this study are secondary data in the form of primary legal materials, namely laws and regulations, and secondary legal materials in the form of writings and other relevant documents. The analysis in this study uses a qualitative approach. The results of this study conclude that patients come to the Health Service Facility when they are sick, which is the legal basis for the legal relationship in health services. After completing the administrative process, the patient will meet Health Human Resources, the Doctor at the Health Service Facility. In this case, a second legal relationship is born based on *informed consent*. After receiving services, the patient must make payments from various existing health financing models in a third-party legal relationship.

Keywords: Law, Legal Relations, Health Services, Health Care Facilities, Health Human Resources, Health Financing, Health Care Practices.

Introduction

According to L.J. Van Apeldoorn, legal relations are relations regulated by law. One of the legal relationships in human activities is in the health field because health is an important aspect of humans. In Law Number 17 of 2023 and Government Regulation Number 28 of 2024 Article 1 paragraph (1), "Health is a healthy state of a person, both physically, mentally, and socially and not just free from disease to enable him to live productively."

To get healthy, it is necessary to make health efforts. The implementation of health efforts is fulfilled with the existence of health services. Health Services are "all activities and/or a series of service activities provided directly to individuals or the Community to maintain and improve public health in promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and/or palliative." The party receiving health services is the patient. This research discusses the legal relations that the patient must understand as part of health efforts.

Research Results

The WHO states that the right to health consists of freedom, where a person can choose about their health, such as reproductive rights, and freedom from pressure, such as from uncommon medical treatment and torture. The right to health means that everyone is entitled to the best health that is maximally pursued as mandated in article 28H: "Everyone has the right to live in physical and mental prosperity, to have a place to live, and to have a good and healthy environment and the right to obtain health services." (Widjaja & Dipo, 2022).

Legal Relationship between Patients and Health Care Facilities in Health Services

The implementation of health services occurs in healthcare facilities. Healthcare facilities are the initial intermediaries that help patients obtain health services when sick. This Health Service Facility is divided into three, namely:

1. First Level Health Care Facility

As defined in Law Number 17 of 2023 concerning Health Article 167 paragraph (1), first-level health service facilities organize primary health care. Primary health care is the health service closest to the community and is the first contact for health services. First-level health service facilities include health centers, private clinics, and independent practices for medical or health workers.

2. Advanced Health Care Facilities

Advanced Health Service Facilities in Law Number 17 of 2023 concerning Health Article 168 paragraph (1) is a Health Service Facility that organizes advanced Health Services covering specialty and/or subspecialty services. In paragraph (2), Advanced Health Service Facilities include hospitals, primary clinics, health centers, and independent medical or health personnel practices.

3. Supporting Health Care Facilities

Supporting Health Service Facilities in Law Number 17 of 2023 concerning Health Article Article 170 paragraph (1) organizes Health Services that support primary Health Services and advanced Health Services. Supporting Health Service Facilities consists of "pharmacy; blood management unit; health

laboratory; stem cell and/or cell processing laboratories; biology material bank; optics; institutions for securing medical devices and facilities; and other supporting health service facilities are to be determined by the minister.”

In the first legal relationship, the Patient will go to the First Level Health Care Facility first and cannot go directly to the Advanced Health Care Facility. At the First Level Health Care Facility, the Patient must complete the administrative process by filling out an administrative form. When filling out the form, there must be an agreement between the patient and the first-level healthcare facility. Consent means there is an agreement. Agreement between parties means a binding agreement between the Patient and the First Level Health Care Facility. This also applies to Advanced Health Care Facilities. In completing the administrative process at the Advanced Health Care Facility, there is a relationship with financing to get a room according to the class that the patient gets.

Human health resources, including medical personnel and health workers, carry out health efforts. Health Care Facility Organizers are prohibited from employing Medical Personnel and Health Personnel who do not have a license to practice in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations. The prohibition must be obeyed because otherwise, it will have a fatal impact on patient's access to health services from health human resources. If Medical and Health Workers practice at Health Service Facilities, the head of the Facility must inform the list of names, SIP and STR numbers, and the practice schedule of Medical and Health Workers. Any Medical Personnel, Health Workers, and leaders of healthcare facilities who do not implement the provisions stipulated in the legislation will be subject to administrative sanctions in the form of:

- a. Oral reprimand;
- b. Written warning;
- c. Administrative fines; and/or
- d. License revocation.

The legal relationship between patients and healthcare facilities, both first-level and advanced healthcare facilities, is a contractual relationship based on the patient's obligation to register and fill in the required forms, which refers to the provisions of Article 1320 of the Civil Code. All elements that constitute the agreement's validity stipulated in Article 1320 of the Civil Code will be filled in at the time of patient registration. An agreement is the patient's consent to obtain health services at a healthcare facility with a contra-presentation to pay money. The agreement with the obligation to provide health services must not be contrary to the law, decency, and general agreement that applies. Therefore, the provisions of Article 1320 of the Civil Code are fulfilled as the basis for the birth of the patient's contractual relationship with the healthcare facility, which allows the patient to obtain further health services (Muljadi & Widjaja, 2004).

Legal Relationship between Patients and Health Human Resources in Health Services

After completing the administrative process, the patient will meet with Health Human Resources, namely Medical Personnel, Health Workers, and Support Workers in Health Service Facilities. The

relationship between Patients and Health Human Resources is a second legal relationship. Health Human Resources Carry out health Efforts in Health Care Facilities.

In carrying out their practice, medical and health workers who provide health services to patients must do their best per norms, service standards, professional standards, and the patient's health needs. Health Human Resources must meet three standards: Professional Standards, Service Standards, and Operational Procedure Standards. However, Best Efforts do not guarantee the Health Services' success or that the patient will recover or get precise results. The purpose of coming to Health Human Resources at Health Care Facilities is not to get a cure (*Result Oriented*). A health service facility and health human resources never say that they are healed. In the provision of Health Services, whether from taking drugs, performing surgery, etc., there are no words guaranteeing success or guaranteeing recovery. Cure is something that has no certainty. So, Health Human Resources only provides Health Services by carrying out the best efforts by the three standards. The Best Practice of Medical and Health Personnel is organized based on an agreement between Medical or Health Personnel and Patients according to the principles of equality and transparency.

In line with the legal relationship between patients and health facilities, the relationship between patients, medical personnel, and health workers also originates from agreements. This means the four requirements in Article 1320 of the Civil Code must also be fulfilled. The provision of Medical and Health Services by Health Human Resources is related to Informed Consent. Informed Consent is an agreement between the patient and the physician to provide medical services to the patient after the patient has received information from the doctor regarding medical efforts that can be made to help him, accompanied by information about all possible risks. In the Minister of Health Regulation No.290 of 2008 concerning Approval of Medical Actions Article 1, the approval of medical action is the consent given by the patient or the closest family after a complete explanation of the medical or dental actions performed on the patient. Everyone has the right to obtain information about their health data, including actions and treatments that have been or will be received from medical personnel and/or health workers. After the patient obtains adequate information and gives consent, medical personnel and/or health workers can carry out health service actions. Explanation of medical acts should include "diagnosis and procedure of medical treatment; the purpose of the medical treatment performed; alternative courses of action and their risks; risks and complications that may occur; prognosis of the action taken; and estimated financing."

The operational definition of Informed Consent is the consent given by the patient (parent, guardian, husband, wife, or person entitled, representing him) to a doctor or health worker to carry out medical actions aimed at curing his illness. Informed Consent shows the relationship between information and consent. In legal aspects, Informed Consent can be summarized as the consent given by the patient or family based on the information provided in Article 1 Paragraph (1) of Permenkes No. 290/MENKES/PER/III/2008 regarding the actions to be taken against the patient. Protecting the individual's right to self-determination is the purpose of Informed Consent. However, after the Patient gets all the information from the doctor, the Patient declares to withdraw from continuing the Health

Effort, and the legal relationship has ended. So, it is not necessarily the case that the Patient coming to the Health Care Facility must complete all the processes from beginning to end.

In providing health services, medical personnel or health workers, in accordance with Article 1339 of the Civil Code, must consider norms, service standards, and professional standards, as well as the health needs of patients. These norms include the Code of Ethics of the Health Facilities, the applicable standard operating procedures, and the Code of Ethics of the applicable Medical or Health Professionals. Professional standards are established by the Council and Collegium and set by the Minister of Health in a Minister of Health Regulation. Four key bioethical principles should determine the health needs of patients, with a focus on patient safety (Widjaja, 2024).

Implementing Health Efforts in the form of Health Services can utilize information and communication technology through Telehealth and Telemedicine, which are integrated with the National Health Information System. In clinical services, health service facilities provide telemedicine, which is carried out by medical or health personnel with STR and SIP. Telehealth provides and facilitates health services, including public health, health information services, and self-service, through telecommunications and digital communication technology. Meanwhile, telemedicine provides and facilitates clinical services through telecommunications and digital communication technology.

The result of Informed Consent is a Medical Record. A Medical Record is a document containing data on the Patient's identity, examination, treatment, actions, and other services provided to the Patient using an electronic system intended to implement medical records. Suppose a healthcare facility cannot organize electronic medical records due to technical obstacles. In that case, non-electronic medical records may be used until the obstacles are resolved and medical record data is re-entangled in the electronic medical record system. Medical Records are the property of Health Service Facilities, which are regulated in Law Number 17 of 2023 concerning Health Article 297 paragraph (1) and Government Regulation Number 28 of 2024 Article 777, Article 784 paragraph (1). The Medical Record document contains data on the Patient's identity, examination, treatment, actions, and other services provided to the Patient, including approval of Health Service actions. Medical personnel and health workers must make and fill out the medical records. Medical Records must be stored and kept confidential by Medical Personnel, Health Workers, and leaders of Health Service Facilities. Government Regulation Number 28 of 2024, Article 779 paragraph (1) states that medical Records must be organized electronically in accordance with statutory provisions.

Electronic Medical Records are regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 24 of 2022 concerning Medical Records. Article 1, paragraph (2) is a Medical Record made using an electronic system intended to implement Medical Records. In Article 3, paragraph (1), every Health Service Facility is required to organize Electronic Medical Records. Electronic Medical Record Storage is an activity of storing Medical Record data on digital-based storage media at Health Service Facilities. The contents of the Medical Record belong to the Patient. Health services professionals enter clinical information into the electronic medical record. The identity and information about the Patient are confidential, so they must be stored and maintained. The patient's personal health secrets are part of the Medical Record, which must be kept by Healthcare

Facilities, Medical Personnel, and Health Workers in carrying out Health Services. Health confidentiality refers to a person's history, condition, and treatment, including physical and psychological health treatment, as well as the patient's data. Meanwhile, what is meant by the Patient's personal Health Secret is everything related to things found by Medical and Health Workers in the context of treatment, recorded in the Patient's medical record, which is confidential. Every Medical and Health Worker carrying out Health Services is obliged to keep the Patient's personal health secrets.

Medical Records containing personal data and patient health information have become "Medical secrets," regulated in Minister of Health Regulation 36 of 2012 concerning medical secrets and Government Regulation 10 of 1966 concerning the obligation to keep medical secrets, which are no longer valid. However, Government Regulation No. 10/1966 on Compulsory Keeping of Medical Secrets is regulated by Government Regulation No. 28/2024 and Law No. 17/2023. In Minister of Health Regulation Number 36 of 2012 Article 1, paragraph 1, Medical Secrets are data and information about a person's health obtained by health workers in their work or profession. Medical Secrets include data and information about "patient identity; the patient's health, including the results of anamnesis; physical examination; supporting examination, diagnosis, treatment, and/or medical treatment; and other matters relating to the patient."

However, it is not uncommon for doctors to commit negligence and medical malpractice against patients. Patients who feel harmed take legal action by reporting the doctor who allegedly committed negligence and medical malpractice to the police with allegations of criminal offenses and even filing legal remedies in the form of tort claims. According to Gunawan Widjaja, medical malpractice is a wrong practice, either due to errors or omissions committed by doctors or other health workers, whether derived from consent or not, which occurs during or as a result of providing medical professional services in accordance with their expertise and abilities and if violated and resulting in injury or loss to the patient, must provide compensation to the patient. Indemnity is an obligation or obligation that arises due to the inability to fulfill a previous obligation or obligation, whether it comes from an agreement or the law (Muljadi & Widjaja, 2004). Compensation can be in the form of a certain amount of money. According to Gunawan Widjaja (2022), a medical action is considered medical malpractice if it meets the following criteria: "1) The medical action is performed without explanation or consent; 2) The medical action is not in accordance with the standard; 3) The medical action is not performed based on the precautionary principle; 4) There is error or negligence in the medical action; and 5) The medical action causes direct harm to the patient. The patient, as the plaintiff, is burdened with proof of medical malpractice. Evidence that can be used includes written evidence, witnesses, expert testimony, and local inspection."

According to Gunawan Widjaja (2022), doctors and patients are bound by an agreement agreed upon by each other, which is binding for both parties, so medical malpractice cannot be considered a tort. Meanwhile, a tort is a form of obligation born from the law due to human actions that violate the law, which is regulated in the Civil Code Article 1365 (Widjaja & Rokayah, 2022). As an obligation that exists due to failure to fulfill an agreed agreement or a breach of promise, compensation can be

demanded, or compensation can also be demanded for violation of the law. The latter is often associated with tort claims. In this case, it is clear that a compensation claim is always based on the legal relationship underlying the birth or occurrence of losses caused by the inability to fulfill or carry out the agreement (Widjaja, 2024).

However, in relation to unlawful acts or unlawful acts, Article 308 paragraph (1) of Law No.17/2023 also expressly states that “Medical Personnel or Health Workers who are suspected of committing unlawful acts in the implementation of Health Services that may be subject to criminal sanctions, must first request a recommendation from the assembly as referred to in Article 304.” This shows that the understanding of unlawful acts or acts has been narrowly defined in Law No.17/2023, which only refers to the criminal aspect and no longer touches the civil aspect (Widjaja, 2024). As a result, health law focuses more on health services and the relationship between patients, health facilities, and/or health workers. This has led to forensic practices, abortion, euthanasia, and informed consent (Widjaja, 2021).

Legal Relationship between Patient and Health Financing in Health Services

After obtaining health services, patients must make payments to healthcare facilities from various existing health financing models; the relationship that occurs here is the third legal relationship. The Health Financing model consists of:

1. Out-of-pocket is a direct relationship between a patient and a health care facility in which patients incur their own costs or make direct payments without assistance or reimbursement from a third party.
2. Corporate Insurance: Coverage is paid by a third party, namely the company where the employee, namely the patient, works. This must be based on an agreement between the patient and his company and an agreement between the company and the healthcare facility. If the Company does not want to bear the payment, the Patient makes an Out-of-pocket payment.
3. Commercial assurance is coverage paid by a third party, namely the Insurance Company, based on an agreement between the Patient and the Insurance Company and then between the Insurance Company and the Health Service Facility.
4. *Social Insurance* (BPJS Health) is regulated by Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System and Presidential Regulation Number 64 of 2020 concerning the Second Amendment to Presidential Regulation Number 82 of 2018 concerning Health Insurance.

Conclusions

In Health Services, there are three legal relationships. In the first legal relationship, when the sick patient comes to the Health Care Facility, this relationship is based on an agreement in the form of filling out an administrative form. The second legal relationship is the Patient with Health Human Resources based on an agreement in the form of *Informed Consent*, the result of which is a Medical Record. In providing Health Services, Health Human Resources must make the *Best Efforts*. The third legal relationship is that the Patient makes payments with the existing Health Financing model, namely Out of Pocket, Corporate Insurance, Commercial Assurance, and BPJS Health; this relationship is

based on an agreement regulated in Article 1233 of the Civil Code and the Law. An example based on the Law is related to paying contributions regulated in Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System and Presidential Regulation Number 64 of 2020 concerning the Second Amendment to Presidential Regulation Number 82 2018 concerning Health Insurance. All agreements in the first to third relationships are subject to Article 1320 of the Civil Code.

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